

DEFORMATION PROPERTIES OF REINFORCED CONCRETE STRUCTURES IN DDY HOT CLIMATES

N.D.Teshabaeva

Senior lecturer at Fergana Polytechnic Institute

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the deformation properties of reinforced concrete structures in a dry hot climate, their moisture and deformation properties at normal humidity.

The deformation properties of reinforced concrete structures in dry hot climates differ from their strength and deformation properties under normal wet temperatures. In dry hot the long-term effects of load.

Without taking into account these factors, their essential qualities are reduced and the quality and durability of reinforced concrete structures reduced due to high temperature and humidity.

In this regard, it is necessary to take into account the effect of temperature on IVG climate, which is not protected from solar radiation, as shown in the SCC 2.03.01.96 [2.4]. and the bending module coefficient $\beta = 0.85$ should be considered.

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radiation, as shown in the SCC 2.03.01.96 [2.4]. and the bending module coefficient $\beta = 0.85$ should be considered.

For example, [3.2.] the study investigated the strength of the reinforced concrete beam fractures made of lightweight concrete in dry hot climates. The theoretical rate, determined by the method of short-term loading on the experimental barrier without the effect of dry hot climate [3.4.], corresponds to the width of the crack opening estimated in the experiment.

Theoretically the normal crack opening width for other beams tested in dry hot climates was 10–25% lower. These experimental samples were subjected to climatic conditions for up to 3 and 20 months after loading. The longer the toxins were in dry hot climates, the more fractures occurred, which did not take into account the theoretical crack opening width [4.5].

Temperature moisture deformation of assembled reinforced concrete elements

depends on daily and year-round changes in the relative humidity of the surrounding environment during operation in Central Asia. The maximum deformation value is 5:00 pm, with the minimum deformation at 4-6 in the morning. The maximum value of the deformation during the year is in the summer and the minimum is in winter.

The results of the experimental tests show that when calculating the reinforced concrete structures it is necessary to take into account the increase in the deformation of the rigidity and the conditions of concrete slabbing, seasonal preparation and use of the element. From the experience, it is shown that the threshold value of winter deformation of concrete is 10% lower than in summer and 25% is lower than in summer. Scientific studies are required for the successful use of reinforced concrete structures by ceramic concrete. [6].

It is important to take into account the urgency of the investigation in the large-scale use of lightweight concrete concrete with a special focus on dry hot climates.

2. The use of new effective composite materials and designs for the technical

improvement of the construction industry in large-scale construction works in our country requires improvement in the production of high-quality and reliable products.

3. One of the most important technical advances in construction is the use of composite fittings in place of steel fittings, thus reducing the weight of buildings and structures.

4. Recently, special attention is paid to the characteristic features of concrete at high temperature and low humidity as a design in dry hot climates.

5. Temperature moisture deformation of aggregate reinforced concrete elements depends on daily and year-round changes in the relative humidity of the surrounding environment during operation in Central Asian climates.

6. Analysis of the work done shows that, based on the data obtained, it is necessary to consider the physical and mechanical properties of concrete in dry hot climates when designing and calculating reinforced concrete structures.

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